

Description of the data files related to the study of label-free quantitative proteomics in *Candida* yeasts species, assessing data reproducibility in technical and biological replicates. All files are available here <http://identifiers.org/pride.project:PXD014125>

Name of data file	Size	File type	Description
Candida_albicans ORF.fasta	4.701 MB	Multi-Fasta file	Candida albicans protein database used for the MS/MS identification step
Candida_glabrata ORF.fasta	3.324 MB	Multi-Fasta file	Candida glabrata protein database used for the MS/MS identification step
1512006-Calbicans-QUANTI.csv	1.921 MB	Results from Progenesis QI for Proteomics software (version 4.1, Waters)	Relative quantification of proteins in Candida albicans (CALB)
1445007-Cglabrata-QUANTI.csv	1.339 MB	Results from Progenesis QI for Proteomics software (version 4.1, Waters) - CSV exported file	Relative quantification of proteins in Candida glabrata (CGLAB)
1445007-Q10-CTRL-60-Cglabrata.pdResult	97.273 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - pdResult exported file	CGLAB (species); CTRL (time course); T60 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1445007-Q11-TRIS1-60-Cglabrata.pdResult	102.199 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - pdResult exported file	CGLAB (species); ALK1 (time course); T60 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1445007-Q12-TRIS2-60-Cglabrata.pdResult	91.676 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - pdResult exported file	CGLAB (species); ALK2 (time course); T60 (time point); REP2 (MS run)

1445007-Q1-CTRL-10-Cglabrata.pdResult	71.98 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - pdResult exported file	CGLAB (species); CTRLR (time course); T10 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1445007-Q2-TRIS1-10-Cglabrata.pdResult	63.023 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - pdResult exported file	CGLAB (species); ALK1 (time course); T10 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1445007-Q3-TRIS2-10-Cglabrata.pdResult	8.055 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - pdResult exported file	CGLAB (species); ALK2 (time course); T10 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1445007-Q4-CTRL-60-Cglabrata.pdResult	97.629 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - pdResult exported file	CGLAB (species); CTRLR (time course); T60 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1445007-Q5-TRIS1-60-Cglabrata.pdResult	98.688 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - pdResult exported file	CGLAB (species); ALK1 (time course); T60 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1445007-Q6-TRIS2-60-Cglabrata.pdResult	54.578 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - pdResult exported file	CGLAB (species); ALK2 (time course); T60 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1445007-Q7-CTRL-10-Cglabrata.pdResult	68.164 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - pdResult exported file	CGLAB (species); CTRLR (time course); T10 (time point); REP2 (MS run)

1445007-Q8-TRIS1-10-Cglabrata.pdResult	93.992 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - pdResult exported file	CGLAB (species); ALK1 (time course); T10 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1445007-Q9-TRIS2-10-Cglabrata.pdResult	9.031 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - pdResult exported file	CGLAB (species); ALK2 (time course); T10 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1512006-10-CTRL-60-Calbicans.pdResult	237.34 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - pdResult exported file	CALB (species); CTRL (time course); T60 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1512006-11-TRIS1-60-Calbicans.pdResult	212.152 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - pdResult exported file	CALB (species); ALK1 (time course); T60 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1512006-12-TRIS2-60-Calbicans.pdResult	231.523 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - pdResult exported file	CALB (species); ALK2 (time course); T60 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1512006-1-CTRL-10-Calbicans.pdResult	268.523 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - pdResult exported file	CALB (species); CTRL (time course); T10 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1512006-2-TRIS1-10-Calbicans.pdResult	235.52 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - pdResult exported file	CALB (species); ALK1 (time course); T10 (time point); REP1 (MS run)

1512006-3- TRIS2-10- Calbicans.pdRes ult	214.60 5 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - pdResult exported file	CALB (species); ALK2 (time course); T10 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1512006-4- CTRL-60- Calbicans.pdRes ult	216.98 8 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - pdResult exported file	CALB (species); CTRL (time course); T60 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1512006-5- TRIS1-60- Calbicans.pdRes ult	200.36 3 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - pdResult exported file	CALB (species); ALK1 (time course); T60 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1512006-6- TRIS2-60- Calbicans.pdRes ult	220.34 4 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - pdResult exported file	CALB (species); ALK2 (time course); T60 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1512006-7- CTRL-10- Calbicans.pdRes ult	209 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - pdResult exported file	CALB (species); CTRL (time course); T10 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1512006-8- TRIS1-10- Calbicans.pdRes ult	226.36 3 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - pdResult exported file	CALB (species); ALK1 (time course); T10 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1512006-9- TRIS2-10- Calbicans.pdRes ult	211.89 8 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - pdResult exported file	CALB (species); ALK2 (time course); T10 (time point); REP2 (MS run)

1445007-Q10-CTRL-60-Cglabrata.xlsx	0.784 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - XLSX exported file	CGLAB (species); CTRLR (time course); T60 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1445007-Q11-TRIS1-60-Cglabrata.xlsx	0.86 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - XLSX exported file	CGLAB (species); ALK1 (time course); T60 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1445007-Q12-TRIS2-60-Cglabrata.xlsx	0.829 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - XLSX exported file	CGLAB (species); ALK2 (time course); T60 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1445007-Q1-CTRL-10-Cglabrata.xlsx	0.424 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - XLSX exported file	CGLAB (species); CTRLR (time course); T10 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1445007-Q2-TRIS1-10-Cglabrata.xlsx	0.53 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - XLSX exported file	CGLAB (species); ALK1 (time course); T10 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1445007-Q3-TRIS2-10-Cglabrata.xlsx	0.048 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - XLSX exported file	CGLAB (species); ALK2 (time course); T10 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1445007-Q4-CTRL-60-Cglabrata.xlsx	0.784 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - XLSX exported file	CGLAB (species); CTRLR (time course); T60 (time point); REP1 (MS run)

1445007-Q5- TRIS1-60- Cglabrata.xlsx	0.838 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - XLSX exported file	CGLAB (species); ALK1 (time course); T60 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1445007-Q6- TRIS2-60- Cglabrata.xlsx	0.53 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - XLSX exported file	CGLAB (species); ALK2 (time course); T60 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1445007-Q7- CTRL-10- Cglabrata.xlsx	0.439 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - XLSX exported file	CGLAB (species); CTRLR (time course); T10 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1445007-Q8- TRIS1-10- Cglabrata.xlsx	0.114 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - XLSX exported file	CGLAB (species); ALK1 (time course); T10 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1445007-Q9- TRIS2-10- Cglabrata.xlsx	0.058 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - XLSX exported file	CGLAB (species); ALK2 (time course); T10 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1512006-10- CTRL-60- Calbicans.xlsx	0.774 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - XLSX exported file	CALB (species); CTRLR (time course); T60 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1512006-11- TRIS1-60- Calbicans.xlsx	0.91 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - XLSX exported file	CALB (species); ALK1 (time course); T60 (time point); REP2 (MS run)

1512006-12- TRIS2-60- Calbicans.xlsx	1.132 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - XLSX exported file	CALB (species); ALK2 (time course); T60 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1512006-1- CTRL-10- Calbicans.xlsx	0.989 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - XLSX exported file	CALB (species); CTRL (time course); T10 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1512006-2- TRIS1-10- Calbicans.xlsx	1.022 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - XLSX exported file	CALB (species); ALK1 (time course); T10 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1512006-3- TRIS2-10- Calbicans.xlsx	0.773 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - XLSX exported file	CALB (species); ALK2 (time course); T10 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1512006-4- CTRL-60- Calbicans.xlsx	0.798 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - XLSX exported file	CALB (species); CTRL (time course); T60 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1512006-5- TRIS1-60- Calbicans.xlsx	0.825 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - XLSX exported file	CALB (species); ALK1 (time course); T60 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1512006-6- TRIS2-60- Calbicans.xlsx	1.03 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - XLSX exported file	CALB (species); ALK2 (time course); T60 (time point); REP1 (MS run)

1512006-7-CTRL-10-Calbicans.xlsx	0.735 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - XLSX exported file	CALB (species); CTRLR (time course); T10 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1512006-8-TRIS1-10-Calbicans.xlsx	0.836 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - XLSX exported file	CALB (species); ALK1 (time course); T10 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1512006-9-TRIS2-10-Calbicans.xlsx	0.782 MB	Results from Proteome Discoverer software (Thermo Scientific, version 2.1) - XLSX exported file	CALB (species); ALK2 (time course); T10 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1445007-Q10-CTRL-60-Cglabrata.raw	1,325.129 MB	Results from Q-Exactive Plus mass spectrometer - Raw data file	CGLAB (species); CTRLR (time course); T60 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1445007-Q11-TRIS1-60-Cglabrata.raw	1,358.611 MB	Results from Q-Exactive Plus mass spectrometer - Raw data file	CGLAB (species); ALK1 (time course); T60 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1445007-Q12-TRIS2-60-Cglabrata.raw	1,291.78 MB	Results from Q-Exactive Plus mass spectrometer - Raw data file	CGLAB (species); ALK2 (time course); T60 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1445007-Q1-CTRL-10-Cglabrata.raw	1,589.549 MB	Results from Q-Exactive Plus mass spectrometer - Raw data file	CGLAB (species); CTRLR (time course); T10 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1445007-Q2-TRIS1-10-Cglabrata.raw	1,280.358 MB	Results from Q-Exactive Plus mass spectrometer - Raw data file	CGLAB (species); ALK1 (time course); T10 (time point); REP1 (MS run)

1445007-Q3-TRIS2-10-Cglabrata.raw	1,407.6 67 MB	Results from Q-Exactive Plus mass spectrometer - Raw data file	CGLAB (species); ALK2 (time course); T10 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1445007-Q4-CTRL-60-Cglabrata.raw	1,363.4 32 MB	Results from Q-Exactive Plus mass spectrometer - Raw data file	CGLAB (species); CTRLR (time course); T60 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1445007-Q5-TRIS1-60-Cglabrata.raw	1,375.9 82 MB	Results from Q-Exactive Plus mass spectrometer - Raw data file	CGLAB (species); ALK1 (time course); T60 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1445007-Q6-TRIS2-60-Cglabrata.raw	1,045.1 34 MB	Results from Q-Exactive Plus mass spectrometer - Raw data file	CGLAB (species); ALK2 (time course); T60 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1445007-Q7-CTRL-10-Cglabrata.raw	1,582.8 74 MB	Results from Q-Exactive Plus mass spectrometer - Raw data file	CGLAB (species); CTRLR (time course); T10 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1445007-Q8-TRIS1-10-Cglabrata.raw	1,379.2 04 MB	Results from Q-Exactive Plus mass spectrometer - Raw data file	CGLAB (species); ALK1 (time course); T10 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1445007-Q9-TRIS2-10-Cglabrata.raw	1,142.9 77 MB	Results from Q-Exactive Plus mass spectrometer - Raw data file	CGLAB (species); ALK2 (time course); T10 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1512006-10-CTRL-60-Calbicans.raw	906.28 7 MB	Results from Q-Exactive Plus mass spectrometer - Raw data file	CALB (species); CTRLR (time course); T60 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1512006-11-TRIS1-60-Calbicans.raw	1,145.8 68 MB	Results from Q-Exactive Plus mass spectrometer - Raw data file	CALB (species); ALK1 (time course); T60 (time point); REP2 (MS run)

1512006-12-TRIS2-60-Calbicans.raw	1,134.2 38 MB	Results from Q-Exactive Plus mass spectrometer - Raw data file	CALB (species); ALK2 (time course); T60 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1512006-1-CTRL-10-Calbicans.raw	1,262.9 66 MB	Results from Q-Exactive Plus mass spectrometer - Raw data file	CALB (species); CTRLR (time course); T10 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1512006-2-TRIS1-10-Calbicans.raw	1,179.9 59 MB	Results from Q-Exactive Plus mass spectrometer - Raw data file	CALB (species); ALK1 (time course); T10 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1512006-3-TRIS2-10-Calbicans.raw	1,173.5 56 MB	Results from Q-Exactive Plus mass spectrometer - Raw data file	CALB (species); ALK2 (time course); T10 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1512006-4-CTRL-60-Calbicans.raw	854.00 6 MB	Results from Q-Exactive Plus mass spectrometer - Raw data file	CALB (species); CTRLR (time course); T60 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1512006-5-TRIS1-60-Calbicans.raw	1,088.7 45 MB	Results from Q-Exactive Plus mass spectrometer - Raw data file	CALB (species); ALK1 (time course); T60 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1512006-6-TRIS2-60-Calbicans.raw	1,099.7 53 MB	Results from Q-Exactive Plus mass spectrometer - Raw data file	CALB (species); ALK2 (time course); T60 (time point); REP1 (MS run)
1512006-7-CTRL-10-Calbicans.raw	949.64 3 MB	Results from Q-Exactive Plus mass spectrometer - Raw data file	CALB (species); CTRLR (time course); T10 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
1512006-8-TRIS1-10-Calbicans.raw	1,127.2 08 MB	Results from Q-Exactive Plus mass spectrometer - Raw data file	CALB (species); ALK1 (time course); T10 (time point); REP2 (MS run)

1512006-9- TRIS2-10- Calbicans.raw	1,164.8 38 MB	Results from Q- Exactive Plus mass spectrometer - Raw data file	CALB (species); ALK2 (time course); T10 (time point); REP2 (MS run)
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